

World Journal on Education and Humanities Research

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Vol. 1, Issue 2, pp. 38-48

Received, January 2022; Revised March 2022;

Accepted March 2022

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6598611>

CAPABILITIES INITIATIVE IN THE TRANSFER OF LEARNING IN NEW ERA

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Abstract:

The main purpose of this study was to determine the teachers' capabilities in using distance learning approach in identified school district in Lapulapu city Division. The researchers used the descriptive research method to gather information about the levels of teacher's capabilities. The data obtained were analyzed using percentage weighted mean, and t-test, utilizing 0.05 level of significance. Results of the study showed teachers were capable in teaching using distance learning, data also suggest that in terms of technological aspects teachers and learners have the basic knowledge. However, it can be noted that there were some aspects in distance learning domains that needs to be improved especially on personalizing instruction and teachers-student interaction. Additionally, governments should take steps to improve the methods of teaching and learning in the new normal of education. Additionally, the findings suggest that the government and private sector should provide immediate support for the development or upgrade of IT infrastructure, the addition of cell sites for internet connectivity, and the expansion of research initiatives in every school, particularly during this time of pandemic. This indicates, that teachers were equipped with the skills and knowledge in giving the best quality of education to the students.

Keywords: Capabilities Initiative, Transfer of Learning, blended learning approach

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly disrupted our education system, changed what classrooms and learned look like on a day-to-day basis (Stanistreet et al., 2020). Educators are navigating a constantly shifting landscape, with the health of students, teachers, and the community at large at stake (Bozkurt et al., 2020; Breslin, 2021). In this series, AIR experts provide their insight into evidence-based practices and approaches for facilitating high-quality instruction from attracting, preparing, and retaining teachers to providing them with professional learning opportunities even during uncertain times. Teacher preparation is designed to train future teachers for the classroom (Darling-Hammond, 2010; Starkey, 2020). High-quality preparation programs provide candidates with the opportunity to apply what they have learned, to

gain hands-on experience in real classrooms, and to work directly with diverse learners in a supervised context (DeGraff et al., 2015). While research on teacher preparation is limited, there is a positive connection between teachers' preparation in their subject matter and their performance. For example, fully prepared special education teachers are not only more likely to remain in the profession; they're also improving outcomes for students with disabilities (Holdheide, 2020).

According to Murphy (2020) while public health officials largely agree that the general threat of COVID-19 is best fought with measures of social distancing, the specific acts of instituting emergency eLearning protocols do not alter the pandemic itself, but only indirectly by limiting face-to-face classroom interactions. Recent articles published have noted that distance learning is now expected to be the major means of education due to social distancing protocol in the schools (Li & Lalani, 2020).

There has been various research to study the significance of distant learning at time of pandemic. Seale (2020) remarked that Education leaders are confronting the unanticipated task of offering remote learning as the dominant method of teaching for weeks, months, and potentially the balance of the school year. Understandably, requiring students to have the technological resources and support at home needed for effective distance learning programs to work is a challenging legal obligation (Koskela et al., 2020). It's extremely likely with the greater exposure to the flexibility Online Learning gives, it will become more incorporated into daily schooling, and eventually become the new normal (Stafford Global, 2020).

The educational practice commonly known as online distance learning has been around for quite some time now. The concept of blended learning dates to the early uses of technology to enhance training in the 1960s, and the term itself has been in use since the advent of the Internet in the 1990 (Saracho, 2019). Moreover, the visualizing potentials of the online means of education was investigated in studies by Tambouris et al. (2014) and Olsson, Mozelius and Collin (2016). Both studies emphasize the extent to which online technologies can be used for creating a learning environment that through visual support represents an added value in students' learning experience.

Research in online distance education has been done largely in the context of western educational settings. Many educational institutions have created solutions to their increasing educational needs through the development of distance education programs (Dhawan, 2020). Distance education allows educational paths to be determined by educators and students, who are separated with physical distance, using technology (Keles and Ozel, 2016). In addition, online distance education is an effective alternative system that can address the current challenge in education and, at the same time, help the marginalized sector, according to the founder of a leading major educational provider (Reyes, 2020).

In the Philippines online distance learning is not new especially in private school, however in public school it is considered as emerging teaching and learning approach. With schools to re-open its doors the following school year, there is a need to strengthen policy in terms of the delivery of instruction to provide opportunities for online learning platforms. Numerous innovative programs have been proposed by different governing bodies in education. The Department of Education emphasized that it would not necessarily mean that teachers and learners will go to schools and learn inside the classrooms and devised various modalities to ensure that online learning a choice among all others in this new learning environment (DepEd, 2020). Similarly, in the higher education institutions, new normal would-be virtual classrooms. The Commission on Higher Education suggested to strengthen online platforms and blended learning such as but not limited to google classroom, messenger, zoom, edmodo

(CHED, 2020). In addition, both will adopt numerous learning delivery options such as but not limited to face-to-face, blended learnings, distance learnings, and home-schooling and other modes of delivery (CHED, 2020; DepEd, 2020).

Moreover, while there has been a significant increase in demand for online distance education and blended learning instructions, there has not been a commensurate increase in efforts to prepare teachers to meet that demand. Moreover, teachers must acquire a certain level of IT competency and proficiency needed for distant online learning to work effectively, learn the ethical standards in using technology, teachers' disposition, the blended activities and assessment, and using personalized instruction (Graham Et al. (2019). Otherwise, this will become a barrier that may hamper the success and effectiveness of blended learning. Among the possible challenges facing teachers include having to grapple with an increased cognitive load, and a vertical and high-ceilinged learning curve, especially for teachers who are not acquainted with this type of delivery mode. Teachers who are not as adjusted and familiar with the dynamics of technology, have to upgrade their aptitude and literacy quickly. This could be more challenging for these teachers than their students.

1. Purpose of the Study

This research determined the teachers' capabilities in using blended learning approach. Level of teacher's capabilities in the transfer of learning through blended learning approach in in the following domain as to instructional methods and assessment & evaluation, and issues and concerns were considered in the main problem of the study.

2. Research Methodology

The researchers utilized the descriptive research method to gather information teachers' preparedness under new normal, together with sets of questionnaires as data gathering instruments. As widely used, descriptive research describes a certain present state. Reasonably, the method is applicable to this study since it aims to describe the current condition. The technique that was used under descriptive method is a survey approach which is normally used to explore opinions according to respondents that can represent a whole population. The data gathered were treated by the aid of statistical software utilizing 0.05 level of significance. Teachers and administrators were the main respondents of the study. The main questionnaire of the study was adopted from the study of Graham et al. (2019) model of instrument development. Specifically, the instrument contained the following top-level areas: instructional methods and strategies and assessment and evaluation.

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of personalizing instruction. Based on the data, the statement " Use student performance data to provide timely help with misconceptions" got the highest weighted mean of 4.91 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. However, the statement " Answer students' course related questions online (in addition to in person)" got the lowest weighted mean of 3.26 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of the teachers on planning activities got an overall mean score of 3.81 which verbally described as knowledgeable

Table 1. Personalizing instruction

Personalizing Instruction	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Use data collected online to customize students' learning experience	3.78	K	3.60	K
Use data collected online to determine which groups or individual students need additional instructional support	3.48	K	4.00	K
Answer students' course related questions online (in addition to in person).	3.26	K	3.00	K
Use student performance data to provide timely help with misconceptions.	4.91	SK	3.6	SK
Address any limitations of educational software through individual or small group instruction.	3.64	K	3.6	K
Weighted mean	3.81	K	3.56	K

There are many benefits to personalized learning, especially through promoting student voice and choice, a flexible learning pace, and the ability to learn anytime, from anywhere. Knowing how to find the most beneficial resources that will empower students to develop their skills in the content area, and have their respective needs met to go about doing this can be a challenge when considering the typical class period length and number of students taught per class. Setting aside time to provide authentic and meaningful feedback to each student and be able to individualize the learning materials is critical for student success (Poth, 2018).

Table 2. Facilitating Student Interaction

Facilitating Student Interaction	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Determine when it is most effective to interact with students online versus in-person.	4.52	SK	2.8	M K
Strengthen caring relationships with students via online communication	4.28	SK	4.00	K
Convey your personality in online text-based communication with students.	4.36	SK	3.00	K
Ensure students are comfortable communicating with you online.	4.22	SK	3.00	M K
Promptly respond to student inquiries online (in addition to in person).	4.12	K	4.00	K
Weighted mean	4.3	SK	3.36	K

Table 2, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of facilitating student interaction. Based on the data, the statement "Determine when it is most effective to interact with students online versus in-person" got the highest weighted mean of 4.52 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. However, the statement "Promptly respond to student inquiries online (in addition to in person)" got the lowest weighted mean of 4.12 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of the teachers on planning activities got an overall mean score of 4.3 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. While administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to promptly respond to student inquiries online (in addition to in person) and strengthen

caring relationships with students via online communication got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as knowledgeable, while the statement refers to determine when it is most effective to interact with students online versus in-person got the lowest weighted mean of 2.8 which verbally described as moderately knowledgeable. Overall, administrators got a final grand mean of 3.36 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Recent findings of Lynch (2018) blended learning that uses apps, games, or measurable programs to teach concepts allows students to engage the material at their own pace. This helps to balance a classroom that contains both quick and slow learners. Every student can practice and tackle new material with timing that is perfect just for them. Hence, student-to-student interaction is a vital part of any course experience.

Table 3. Facilitating Student-Content Interaction

Facilitating Student-Content Interaction	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Facilitate students' small group discussions online (in addition to in person).	3.53	K	3.60	K
Facilitate students' small group collaboration on projects online (in addition to in person).	3.48	K	3.40	K
Strengthen students' sense of belonging to the classroom community using online communication	4.16	K	3.60	K
Monitor students' online interactions with each other to ensure quality participation	4.21	K	3.60	K
Create opportunities for students to teach each other inside and outside of class using online technology.	3.64	K	3.40	K
Weighted mean	3.80	K	3.52	K

Table 3, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of facilitating student-content interactions. Based on the data, the statement " Monitor students' online interactions with each other to ensure quality participation" got the highest weighted mean of 4.21 which verbally described as knowledgeable. However, the statement " Facilitate students' small group discussions online (in addition to in person)" got the lowest weighted mean of 3.48 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of the teachers on planning activities got an overall mean score of 3.80 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to facilitate students' small group discussions online, strengthen students' sense of belonging to the classroom community using online communication and monitor students' online interactions with each other to ensure quality participation got the highest weighted mean of 3.60 which verbally described as knowledgeable, while the statement refers to facilitate students' small group collaboration on projects online and create opportunities for students to teach each other inside and outside of class using online technology got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, administrators' data got a final mean of 3.52 which verbally described as knowledgeable. According to Pinantoan (2013) key players in distance education typically include students, faculty, facilitators, support staff function effectively as a skilled facilitator as well as content provider. The ability to interact with more people from varied backgrounds and this attitude bleeds over into faculty and even students.

Table 4, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of implementing assessments. Based on the data, the statement " Use data from online and offline assessments to identify

patterns in group and whole class learning gaps" got the highest weighted mean of 4.61 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. However, the statement "Use online and traditional grading rubrics to clearly identify individual student performance gaps" got the lowest weighted mean of 4.22 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable.

Table 4. Implementing Assessment

Implementing Assessments	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Administer performance-based assessments online.	4.46	SK	3.40	K
Use online tools to provide students with opportunities for reflective self-assessment.	4.32	SK	4.00	K
Use online and traditional grading rubrics to clearly identify individual student performance gaps	4.22	SK	3.00	K
Use data from online and offline assessments to identify patterns in group and whole class learning gaps.	4.61	SK	3.60	MK
Help students use online and offline assessment data to guide their own learning progress.	4.26	SK	4.00	K
Weighted mean	4.37	SK	3.36	K

Overall, the knowledge of the teachers on planning activities got an overall mean score of 4.37 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. Planning out your assessments and leveraging technology tools for assessment are critical steps for setting up effective practices for the blended learning classroom. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to use online tools to provide students with opportunities for reflective self-assessment and help students use online and offline assessment data to guide their own learning progress got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as knowledgeable while the statement refers to administer performance-based assessments online got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, administrators' data got a final mean of 3.36 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Matt Miller (2015) argues that one of the key components to success in the blended learning classroom is the assessment piece. He specifically mentions formative assessment and how instructors should utilize the platforms or tools that are already in place to effectively monitor student progress. This indicates that teachers have the knowledge in conducting varied assessment in distance education.

Table 5, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of evaluating and reflecting. Based on the data, the statement "Use student performance data to evaluate the effectiveness of teachers' online instruction" got the highest weighted mean of 4.51 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. However, the statement " Use student performance data to evaluate the effectiveness of how online and in-person activities and assessments were blended together" got the lowest weighted mean of 4.02 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of the teachers on planning activities got an overall mean score of 4.25 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to use student performance data to evaluate the effectiveness of teachers' online instruction and collaborate with other teachers to evaluate the effectiveness of units that blend online and in-person instruction got the highest weighted mean of 3.80 which verbally described as knowledgeable, while the statement refers to use student performance data

to evaluate the effectiveness of online educational materials and assessments and use student performance data to evaluate the effectiveness of how online and in-person activities and assessments were blended together got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as knowledgeable.

Table 5. Evaluating and Reflecting

Evaluating and reflecting	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Use student performance data to evaluate the effectiveness of teachers' online instruction.	4.51	SK	3.80	K
Use student performance data to evaluate the effectiveness of online educational materials and assessments	4.43	SK	3.40	K
Use student performance data to evaluate the effectiveness of how online and in-person activities and assessments were blended together	4.02	K	3.40	K
Provide students with multiple opportunities to provide input about the effectiveness of the online and in-person teaching strategies.	4.11	K	3.60	K
Collaborate with other teachers to evaluate the effectiveness of units that blend online and in-person instruction.	4.16	K	3.80	K
Weighted mean	4.25	SK	3.60	K

Overall, administrators got a final mean of 3.60 which verbally described as knowledgeable. According to Tuomainen (2017) the role of evaluation is therefore significant in engaging students in distance learning and enhancing their behavioral, emotional and cognitive processes. This is particularly poignant when developing academic and field-specific language skills in an online environment.

Table 6. Test of Significant Difference

Domain	Mean	Pvalue	Decision
Personalizing Instruction	3.81 3.56	0.4412	Failed to reject Ho
Student Interaction	4.30 3.36	0.0401	Reject Ho
Student teacher interaction	3.57 3.60	0.8882	Failed to reject Ho
Student-content interaction	3.80 3.52	0.0987	Failed to reject Ho
Implementing assessment	4.37 3.60	0.018	Reject Ho
Evaluating and reflecting	4.24 3.60	0.005	Reject Ho

Table 6 shows the significant difference between teachers and administrators' perception on the teachers' capabilities in distance learning. Data show that difference was seen on the aspect of student interaction, implementing assessment and evaluating and reflecting, it was shown that its highly significant. While, personalizing instruction,

student-teacher interaction and student-content interaction were failed to reject the hypothesis, this indicates that there is no significant difference on these domains.

Table 7. Issues and Concerns

ISSUES AND CONCERNS	Rank
Lack of ICT resources	4
Internet connection is intermittent	1
Cell sites and internet signal is slow	2
Facilities are not equipped with advance technology	3
Computers are slow and not applicable in current set-up	5
Lack of training in relation to new trends of computer	6

Table 7 shows the issues and concerns perceived by the teachers and learners. Data shows internet connection is intermittent was rated as rank no. 1, followed by cell cite and internet signal is slow, facilities are not equipped with advance technology, lack of ICT resources, computers are slow and not applicable in current set-up, lack of specialists in doing action research, lack of training in relation to new trends of computer.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the rapid changes in the world due to the COVID-19 pandemic have led to challenges faced in our education system. Findings shows that teachers were capable in teaching using distance learning, data also suggest that in terms of technological aspects teachers and learners have the basic knowledge. However, it can be noted that there were some aspects in distance learning domains that needs to be improved especially on personalizing instruction and teachers-student interaction. Additionally, governments should take steps to improve the methods of teaching and learning in the new normal of education. Additionally, the findings suggest that the government and private sector should provide immediate support for the development or upgrade of IT infrastructure, the addition of cell sites for internet connectivity, and the expansion of research initiatives in every school, particularly during this time of pandemic.

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